

Rapid Prototyping Applications in Various Field of Engineering and Technology

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Abstract : In the product design and development process, the prototyping or model making is one of the important step to finalize a product which helps in conceptualization of a design. Rapid Prototyping (RP) is layer-by-layer material deposition started during early 1980s with the enormous growth in Computer Aided Design and Manufacturing (CAD/CAM) technologies. When almost unambiguous solid models with knitted information of edges and surfaces could define a product and also manufacturing by CNC machining. This paper provides a better platform for researchers, new learners and product manufacturers for various applications of RP models. Subsequently it creates awareness among the peoples of recently developing RP method of manufacturing in product design, developments and its applications.

Keywords : prototyping, layer-by-layer, CAD/CAM, product design

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